

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

BIOLOGICAL COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF HIRKAN LEOPARD, CHEETAH AND JAGUAR

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Abstract

This article is dedicated to cheetah, leopard and jaguar which are considered to be the main predator of the ecosystem and members of the cheetah family. If we say that the most beautiful predators are cats we would not be making a mistake. Cheetah, leopard, and jaguar can look very similar at first glance for the shape of their body, their similar colors but they are actually distinguished for their sizes, patterns of their skins, their spreading areal, their lifestyle, and for other features. The author formed and analyzed characteristics of cheetah, leopard and jaguar in morphological, etiological characteristics in comparison form information about different features of black panther also takes place in this article. Author biologically characterized the Hirkan leopard which is currently the biggest leopard.

Keywords: cats, biological comparative characteristics, leopard, of Hirkan Leopard, cheetah, jaguar, Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of Azerbaijan

As is well known, peak consumers of an ecosystem have a major impact on food relations and energy circulation. In recent years, the anthropogenic factor has led to the extinction of large mammals, especially various members of the feline group of predators. In order to solve the problem, special attention is paid in the

Republic of Azerbaijan to the protection of cats, as in the world. Therefore, the study of biological and ecological characteristics of different species of cats has become even more relevant. This article is devoted to the analysis of the comparative biological characteristics of the cheetah, leopard, Hirkan leopard and jaguar.

Picture. 1. Caucasian Leopard caught on camera traps in Astara[8].

Leopard - in Latin it is called *Panthera pardus*. Leopards are also called leopards or tigers. The leopard belongs to the domain of eukaryotes, fauna, chordates, mammals, predators, panthers, leopards. The leopard's current name is *panther pardus* from the Latinized Greek word – *πάνθηρ panther*-from emerged [3]. For the first time, Carl Linnaeus defined the leopard's position in the systematics and called it *felis pardus*. Although the Caucasus leopard and Chinese leopard are listed as subspecies in some literatures, zoologists such as Q.T.Mustafayev, A E Brem, and others do not accept the term subspecies as incomplete as a systematic unit. I don't think it can be a subspecies. Because kind is a whole concept. The units that make up its completeness

together form a type. In other words, it is not considered a species. Therefore, the species of leopard, which vary to some extent depending on the ecological and geographical conditions, are more in line with the concepts of subspecies. So, the Caucasian leopard is as diverse as the Indian leopard and the Chinese leopard.

The leopard is listed in the Red Data Book of Azerbaijan and the International Union for Conservation of Nature (WWF) and is endangered. Its body length is 120-170 cm, tail up to 95 cm, adults weigh 32-60 kg, males weigh up to 75 kg, and females are slightly smaller (1). The weight of the nymphs also varies. For example, the Ceylon leopard has less weight than the African leopard. However, in any species, the

weight of males is greater than the weight of females. The leopard has shaped, not very long, strong muscular legs, round head, soft, densely hairy, black or brown spots, on the sides of the back, around the mouth, dark brown on the head, light brown under the belly. The points are rosette-shaped. Black dots are arranged on the edge of the rosette, the inside is dark brown. Zoologists and ecologists have determined that the leopard's patterns, which appear to us to be identical, are individual. That is, they have different patterns for each individual, like human handprints. The leopard's black-spotted brown color is an ideal camouflage, making it invisible among the leaves of grasses, shrubs and trees. They have relatively short, muscular legs, not as long and thin as cheetahs. The white 90-95 cm tail with a white tip provides balance to the body in long jumps and turns during a prey attack. The paws are strong and muscular. The leopard's movements - gait, jumps - are very beautiful, calm, strong, plastic and flexible. He jumps very gently on high stones and rocks. The leopard can jump up to 5-8 m. The maximum running speed is 58 kilometers per hour. Due to its strong jaw and legs, it can climb trees quickly, unlike the fastest running cheetah on land. AEBrem identify 25 subspecies. In his book, AEBrem describes the different characteristics of leopards and panthers.

As for the reproductive characteristics of leopards, we can say that their gestation period is 92-95 days. They give birth to 2-4 puppies weighing 500-700 kg each. The eyes of blindfolded children open after 20 days. But there are more 1-2 children. Puppies gain hunting skills and defensive tactics by playing with the white tip of the mother leopard's tail. When the children are 1-1.5 years old, the leopard family breaks up. Puppies are born and separated. Each female puppy reaches sexual maturity at about 2 years of age. Leopards are lizards. They live alone. At the age of one, puppies have canine teeth. Sick chicks are eaten by females. There may be 2 or 3 teeth in the area of 40-50 thousand hectares. Females need 20,000 hectares. First of all, the atropogenic factor reduced the area of the leopard, thus creating obstacles for their feeding and reproduction. Therefore, The main reasons for their decline are illegal hunting and shrinking habitats. Unlike leopards, unlike tigers, it hides its manure by burying it. They can easily

climb trees and lift heavy hunting carcasses. The lifespan of a leopard is 11-17 years. They can live in the zoo for more than 22-23 years.

Leopards walk quietly, like to lie in ambush, love cleanliness. Otherwise, body odor would prevent an ambush. Although they are active all day, they become more active at night and in the morning and go hunting. They sleep more during the day. Has strong hearing and vision skills. Unlike jaguars and cheetahs, they are more sensitive to humans.

The leopard is a typical representative of the tropical and subtropical zones. It is found in leopards from Africa to the Far East. It is less adapted to deep snow cover and cold climates. However, in the event of snow in Azerbaijan, the photo was recorded. In Azerbaijan, these animals are found in the dense forests of the Talysh Mountains, in the forested and rocky areas of the Lesser Caucasus, especially in the ravines and rocky outcrops of Kalbajar, Lachin, Nakhchivan hard rocks. In recent years, a leopard has also been found in Mingachevir. They have no natural enemies in Azerbaijan. It can only be killed by humans. Sometimes floods and so on. may be lost during events. The distribution of the leopard depends on the animals it feeds on. The food of the Hirkan leopard living in the Talis Mountains is wild boars, roe deer, arrow hedgehogs and badgers. They can also eat carcasses. Feeding is also reduced during mating. In the Lesser Caucasus, mountain goats are also formed, and in Nakhchivan, mountain sheep are also formed. They eat 2-3 kg of meat at a time. Without food, leopards can go hungry for 7-11 days. Leopards lead a sedentary lifestyle. Sometimes young individuals can go in search of new territories. In ancient times, it was believed that the Leopard is a hybrid of a lion and a panther. Anthropological excavations show that the ancient common ancestor, like all panthers, appeared 11 million years ago, and the modern ancestor of the leopard 3.8 million years ago. Molecular phylogenetic results obtained by various methods show that the species of the genus *Panthera* are closely related to each other. Of the common ancestor, the leopard was formed as a species after the tiger and the leopard, and long before the lion and the jaguar [5]. The European leopard has become extinct.

Picture. 2. Black leopard (*Panthera pardus*).

In nature, the most beautiful of the panthers - black leopards - is rarely found. The first photo of a black jaguar was taken in 2009 by a "trap camera" in the Alberto Manuel Brenes Biological Reserve in Costa Rica [7]. The color of the black leopard is associated with an abundance of melanin pigment. The black color of the skin is a monogenetic recessive trait, and melanistic leopards can be born from the parents of ordinary spotted leopards. When these recessive genes from both parents come together (presumably), the baby may be black. Black leopards are less common because they are less likely. Black pigmented melanistic leopards are more common in India. Rarely in Africa (except the Great Sahara), Central and South Asia, rarely in Azerbaijan (Lankaran and Nakhchivan), in the mountains of southwestern and southern Turkmenistan,

According to Sanderson, a black leopard is the same as a leopard, except that it is black. Sanderson points out that the black leopard is found in dense forests, on the Mallaksko Peninsula, in southern India - Travankure, Maysure. It is more abundant in the south than in the northern forests. Leopards and black

leopards have different temperaments, characters and adaptations.

The protection measures taken by the Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of Azerbaijan in recent years to protect endangered leopards are yielding positive results. The World Wildlife Fund (WWF) first set up a photo trap in 2007 and recorded three leopards. At present, it is found in Hirkanda, Shahdag National Park and Zuvand Reserve in Azerbaijan. There are 11 leopards in Karabakh, 16 in Talysh and 16 in Nakhchivan. Six leopards fell into the cameras installed in Hirkan National Park, which covers an area of 40,350 hectares. This time, more than 20 photo traps installed in Hirkan National Park captured interesting images. Along with leopards, other animals were also captured in the video and photo footage.

On January 11, 2019, another leopard was recorded in Hirkan National Park. IDEA Public Union, in cooperation with the World Wildlife Fund (WWF), recorded the leopard's photos through photo traps during the next monitoring of the restoration of the leopard population in the Hirkan National Park.

Table 1.

Comparative features of panthers.

Season of cats		
Hepard genus, Hepard (<i>Acinonyx jubatus</i>), type.	Leopard genus, Leopard (<i>Panthera pardus</i>) species.	Hepard genus, a type of jaguar (<i>Panthera onca</i>)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It moves at a speed of 120 km / h, sometimes reaching 140 km / h. It is the fastest animal on land. ➤ The body is 1.5 cm, height 85-90 cm, weight 45-70 kg. ➤ Lean has long legs. ➤ The distance between the steps reaches 15 meters. ➤ Can't open the claws until the end. ➤ He can't climb a tree. ➤ It lives in the semi-deserts, savannas and deserts of West and South Africa. ➤ The patterns consist of single points. ➤ There are black stripes on the edge of the mouth. ➤ He is a skilled hunter on land. ➤ He is active at any time of the day. He also hunts during the day. ➤ No attacks were reported. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It moves at a speed of 59 km / h. ➤ Height is 60-70 cm. ➤ Length 120-170 cm, tail length 95 cm. ➤ Males weigh 75 kg, females 32-60 kg. Hirkan leopard can weigh up to 110 kg. ➤ The body is muscular legs are short. ➤ He can open his claws to the end. ➤ It grows very well on trees, it is in trees more than on the ground. ➤ He is a skilled hunter both on water and on land. ➤ It is very aggressive. ➤ The patterns are in the form of a socket, closely spaced. ➤ It is more common in temperate and subtropical forests. ➤ Widespread in Asia and Africa. ➤ Black is more common in leopards. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ It is bigger than a leopard. ➤ According to the results of recent studies, the Hirkan leopard was ahead of it. ➤ Height is 63-78 cm. ➤ The head is round and large. ➤ Usually spotted, very rarely black. It is rosette-shaped. ➤ It has 9 types. ➤ Lives in tropical forests (More, in the Amazon). ➤ It is very common in South America. ➤ When mating, females choose males. ➤ Couples rarely argue when choosing ➤ Men do not recognize their offspring and can eat them. ➤ If they do not hurt, they do not show aggression. ➤ He eats only fresh meat, not carcasses

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Although he likes to lie in wait, he does not lead a secret life. ➤ Less than 7,000 individuals remain. ➤ Area of the area 34-1500 km². ➤ Lives more than 20-25 years. ➤ She gives birth to 2-6 puppies and is 85-95 days pregnant. ➤ They do not reproduce indoors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Lives 10-15 years, 22 years in the zoo. ➤ They reproduce indoors. ➤ 20-50ha for males, 20ha for females. needed. ➤ He is more aggressive than others. ➤ When they mate, they fight to the death for the females. ➤ He goes hunting more often at night and in the morning. ➤ He eats both fresh meat and carcasses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 25-50 sq. M. Km area required ➤ The jaw looks square. ➤ She is a little more than 3 months pregnant and has 2-4 children. ➤ Lives 12 -15 years.
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The leopard is at the top of the ecological pyramid in natural ecosystems. Therefore, it plays a special role in regulating the processes in the ecosystem, their sustainability and maintaining the balance in nature. Leopard living in Azerbaijan usually leads a dark and nocturnal lifestyle. In general, leopards lead a secretive lifestyle. Although this animal is careful, it is not cowardly. They are extremely aggressive when confronted with people. Leopards are very pure animals. Their mating is observed throughout the year. But babies are usually born in the spring and fall. The number of leopards in Azerbaijan is rapidly declining and is in danger of extinction. In the past, many tigers, leopards, etc. were found in the Hirkan reserve [4, p. 379]. The main reason for its extinction in Azerbaijan was the destruction of hunting and habitat. Deforestation, unplanned settlement, etc. caused the leopard's range to shrink and disappear. As the area shrinks, the number of wild ungulates, the leopard's main food, also decreases. Of course, illegal hunting has also sharply reduced the number of ungulates.

In 2014, the Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of Azerbaijan, as well as a group led by Leyla Aliyeva, international organizations, including zoologists and ecologists of the Wildlife Fund, invited the Baku-International Caucasus Cat Summit to the public and announced the results of Hirkan leopard research. According to these studies, the Hirkan leopard has gained the status of the largest living leopard today.

As a result, we can say that different species of leopards and cheetahs of the cat family, along with

similarity, have different biological, ecological and etiological characteristics given in the article. In recent years, leopard conservation measures in the Republic of Azerbaijan have yielded positive results, and their number has increased. As a result of joint research conducted by the IDEA public association, the Ministry of Ecology and Natural Resources of Azerbaijan and the VTF (WWF), the Hirkan leopard has gained the status of "the largest leopard" among the leopard species currently living in the world.

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